

Periodate as an Analytical Reagent. Part I.

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Metaperiodate has been used for the estimation of sodium sulphide, sodium sulphite, sodium bisulphite, sodium dithionite and sodium thiosulphate present alone or in a mixture of two or more of the compounds.

In borax medium, metaperiodate reacts with sulphide, sulphite, bisulphite, dithionite and thiosulphate quantitatively in accordance with the equations :

In the present investigations an attempt has been made to determine these compounds quantitatively by using metaperiodate as a volumetric reagent.

From the equations 1 to 5 it is clear that all the sulphur compounds are oxidised to sulphate whereas periodate is reduced to iodate. The reaction, except in the case of dithionite, is not instantaneous. An excess of periodate is, therefore, always taken and after a suitable interval of time the residual periodate is determined. The net titre of periodate corresponds to the amount of sulphur compound present. In case of sulphide and thiosulphate, the reaction being slow in cold, heating for a suitable time period has been resorted to. The method is quite suitable for the determination of small amounts of sulphide and thiosulphate since they consume eight equivalents of periodate each. At the initial stage, on the addition of sulphide solution to periodate, some colloidal sulphur is precipitated which ultimately disappears on heating.

In the case of dithionite, although direct titration is possible but is of little practical value since sulphite which is always present with dithionite as an impurity also reacts. This interference has been eliminated by adding formaldehyde to convert sulphite into formaldehyde bisulphite and dithionite into formaldehyde bisulphite and formaldehyde sulfoxylate¹.

In the present investigations it has been observed that formaldehyde bisulphite does not react with metaperiodate in acetic acid medium whereas sulfoxylate reacts readily according to the equation :

so a direct titration is possible.

It has been shown that bisulphite, dithionite and thiosulphate (equations 3, 4 and 5) liberate acid which has been estimated and forms an alternate method for the estimation of these compounds. This method is to be particularly recommended in the case of dithionite since solid can be directly weighed into periodate solution thereby avoiding atmospheric oxidation of dithionite in solution. Sulphite does not interfere.

An analysis of a mixture of sulphide and thiosulphate has been made possible by utilising the fact that both are oxidised by periodate but the acid is liberated only by thio-sulphate. The amount of metaperiodate consumed determines both sulphide and thio-sulphate whereas the acid liberated corresponds to thiosulphate alone.

Similarly, a mixture of sulphite, bisulphite and dithionite has been analysed by utilising the fact that all the three compounds are oxidised to sulphate by metaperiodate but only bisulphite and dithionite liberate acid. It has been further shown that only dithionite reacts with metaperiodate in acetic acid medium in presence of formaldehyde. From the amounts of metaperiodate used for all, the amount of acid liberated and the amount of metaperiodate consumed for dithionite alone the quantities of sulphite, bisulphite and dithionite have been calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Estimation of Sulphide—Method I :—A known volume of standardised sulphide solution was added to an excess of standard metaperiodate solution containing 20 ml. of saturated borax solution. The reaction mixture was boiled for about 10 min., cooled and the unreacted metaperiodate was determined iodometrically in a buffered solution². The net titre of metaperiodate corresponded to sulphide present in the solution. The results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I

Sod. sulphide taken (mg)	Sod. sulphide found by Method I (mg)	Sod. sulphide found by Method II (mg)
16.5	16.4	16.6
24.7	24.8	24.6
34.5	34.6	34.7
51.7	51.6	51.7
69.0	69.1	69.1

2. E. Muller and G. Wegelin, *Z. anal. chem.*, 1913, **52**, 755; H. H. Willard and L. H. Grethouses, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **60**, 2869.

Method II :—The sulphide solution was mixed with excess of standard metaperiodate containing sodium hydroxide solution (normality of the solution w.r.t. sodium hydroxide was 2.5 N approx.). The solution was boiled for 10 min., cooled and the unreacted metaperiodate was determined iodometrically in acidic medium³. The results are recorded in Table I.

Estimation of Sulphite :—A known volume of standardised sulphite solution, stabilised towards atmospheric oxidation with ethanol, was added to an excess of standard metaperiodate solution containing 20 ml. of saturated borax solution. After allowing the reaction mixture to stand at room temperature for about 5 min., the unreacted metaperiodate was determined in buffered solution as before. The net titre of metaperiodate corresponded to sulphite present in the solution. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Sod. sulphite taken (mg)	Sod. sulphite found (mg)
25.8	25.9
39.7	39.7
46.1	46.3
51.7	51.0
69.4	69.6

Estimation of Bisulphite—Method I :—The standardised sample solution, stabilised with ethanol was mixed with excess of metaperiodate containing 20 ml. of saturated borax solution. After 5 min., the unreacted metaperiodate was determined as usual. The results are recorded in Table III.

Method II :—This method is based on the determination of the acid liberated when bisulphite is oxidised by metaperiodate (eq. 3).

The standardised bisulphite solution was added to an excess of metaperiodate solution containing standard borax solution in excess. After 5 min., the residual broax was titrated against a standard solution of hydrochloric acid using methyl red as the indicator. The net titre of borax corresponded to bisulphite in the solution. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Sod. bisulphite taken (mg)	Sod. bisulphite found by Method I (mg)	Sod. bisulphite found by Method II (mg)
32.2	31.7	32.2
41.6	41.2	41.3
48.4	47.8	48.4
64.5	64.5	64.5
83.2	83.1	83.0

3. I. M. Kolthoff, R. Bolcher, V. A. Stenger and G. Matsuyama, *Volumetric Analysis*, Vol. III, Interscience Publishers, 1957, p. 273.

Estimation of Dithionite (hyposulphite)—Method I :—The standardised dithionite solution, treated with formaldehyde, was acidified with 10 ml. of 20% acetic acid. The reaction mixture was titrated against a standard solution of metaperiodate to the starch end point. The results are given in Table IV.

Method II :—A known weight of the solid was directly weighed into an excess of metaperiodate solution containing standard solution of borax in excess. After 5 min., the residual borax was titrated as before. The amount of dithionite was calculated from the net titre of borax which corresponded to the acid set free by dithionite (eq. 4). The results are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Sod. dithionite taken (mg)	Sod. dithionite found by Method I (mg)	Sod. dithionite found by Method II (mg)
28.7	28.7	28.6
37.9	37.8	38.0
60.0	60.2	60.1
67.8	67.9	67.9
90.3	90.5	90.3

Estimation of Thiosulphate—Method I :—The standardised sodium thiosulphate solution was mixed with an excess of standard metaperiodate solution, containing 20 ml. of saturated borax solution. The reaction mixture was boiled for 5 min., cooled and the unreacted metaperiodate was determined by iodometric method in buffered solution as before. The results are given in Table V.

Method II :—To an excess of metaperiodate solution, containing a standard solution of borax in excess, was added thiosulphate solution. The reaction mixture was boiled for 5 min., cooled and unreacted borax was titrated as before. The results are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Sod. thio- sulphate taken (mg)	Sod. thio- sulphate found by Method I (mg)	Sod. thio- sulphate found by Method II (mg)
20.0	20.5	19.8
30.0	30.1	29.9
40.0	40.1	40.3
46.5	45.5	46.3
62.0	62.4	62.6

Analysis of a mixture of Sulphide and Thiosulphate :—The sample solution was added to an excess of standard solution of metaperiodate containing standard borax solution in excess. The reaction mixture was boiled for 5 min., cooled and the residual borax was determined as before. From the solution titrated for residual borax, unreacted metaperiodate was determined iodometrically. The results are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Sulphide taken (mg)	Thiosulphate taken (mg)	Sulphide found (mg)	Thiosulphate found (mg)
33.7	33.2	33.4	33.4
22.5	49.8	21.9	50.3
45.0	33.2	44.8	33.4
36.0	24.8	36.3	24.7
27.0	37.2	27.1	37.2
18.0	49.6	18.2	49.6

Analysis of a mixture of Sulphite, Bisulphite and Dithionite :—The solution of the mixture was added to an excess of standard metaperiodate solution containing standard borax solution in excess. After 5 min., the unreacted borax was titrated against standard hydrochloric acid as before. The net titre of borax corresponded to bisulphite and dithionite. From the same solution, unreacted metaperiodate was determined as before. The net titre of metaperiodate corresponded to sulphite, bisulphite and dithionite. The dithionite alone was determined by taking an aliquot of the original mixture solution and titrating it against metaperiodate in acetic acid medium after inactivating bisulphite and sulphite with formaldehyde. From the reagents consumed in the above estimations, the quantities of sulphite, bisulphite and dithionite were calculated (Table VII).

TABLE VII

Bisulphite taken (mg)	Sulphite taken (mg)	Dithionite taken (mg)	Bisulphite found (mg)	Sulphite found (mg)	Dithionite found (mg)
21.8	5.8	14.1	21.8	5.6	14.3
32.7	8.1	21.7	32.3	8.3	21.7
21.8	12.1	28.7	21.3	12.5	28.9
32.7	15.0	34.8	32.7	15.0	35.0
43.6	8.1	21.7	43.6	8.2	21.7

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